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PROCEEDINGS
OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
LOCAL GOVERNANCE, DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION,
AND REGIONAL SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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NHÀ XUẤT BẢN LAO ĐỘNG

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THE EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL AND ITS IMPLICATIONS TO THE EUROPEAN UNION COOPERATION WITH VIETNAM

Case Study: The climate-responsive digital circular economy as a first priority area of action

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Abstract: *The European Green Deal is a new growth strategy adopted by the Eu in response to the climate and environmental-related challenges facing not only the Europe but the whole world. Taking into account that the EU is currently one of Vietnam's largest export markets, with an increasing growth rate under the positive and pervasive impact of the EU-Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA), monitoring and adapting to policies within the framework of the EU Green Deal is a necessary requirement for Vietnam to maintain and develop sustainably in the EU market. Given the dynamic and positive developments of the EU-Vietnam partnership over time, the EU is committed to supporting Vietnam in achieving a just energy transition and fulfilling its national and international climate ambitions. Therefore, in the light of this long-standing commitment, the purpose of this study is analysing the impact of European Green Deal on the priority areas of the EU's bilateral cooperation with Vietnam over the period 2021-2027, the emphasis being on actions taken in relation to the climate-responsive digital circular economy.*

Keywords: *European Green Deal; EU-Vietnam partnership; 2021-2027 Multiannual Indicative Programme for Vietnam; Climate-responsive digital circular economy.*

1. Introduction

Guided by the ambitious purposes established in Article 2 of the Paris Agreement adopted under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (which took place in December 2015)¹, the European Commission has set out a new growth strategy that aims to transform the Union into a fair and prosperous society, with a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy, where there are

¹ This Agreement, in enhancing the implementation of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change adopted in 1992, including its objective, aims to strengthen the global response to the threat of climate change, in the context of sustainable development and efforts to eradicate poverty - https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/english_paris_agreement.pdf

no net emissions of greenhouse gases in 2050 and where economic growth is decoupled from resource use. Thus, "the European Green Deal" - as it was entitled by the Commission in its communication of 11 December 2019 - is a set of policies that reaffirm the EU's commitment to tackling environmental and climate challenges, which form the defined task of the current generation. The European Green Deal (EGD) also aims to protect, conserve and enhance the Union's natural capital, and protect the health and well-being of citizens from environment-related risks and impacts. At the same time, this transition must be just and inclusive, leaving no one behind.²

In this sense, it was stated that the EU has the collective ability to transform its economy and society to put it on a more sustainable path. It can build on its strengths as a global leader on climate and environmental measures, and must be at the forefront of coordinating international efforts towards building a coherent financial system that supports sustainable solutions. Even so, it must be emphasized that the environmental ambition of the Green Deal will not be achieved by Europe acting alone, that's because the drivers of climate change and biodiversity loss are global and are not limited by EU borders. As a result, to achieve its goal of creating a viable and internationally competitive economy, the EU needs to mobilise not only its neighbours but also its partners in all parts of the globe to join it on a sustainable path, especially South-East Asian states.

As one of the most dynamic areas of the world economically - a factor which largely accounts for its growing international significance - the Southeast Asia region is pivotal in efforts to accelerate the shift towards resource-efficient and environmentally friendly economic and growth models. But, in order to make cooperation with countries in this region useful for both sides, however the Europeans first need to ask themselves how the EU vision of a sustainable economy is perceived on the Asian continent, and they also have to take note of the fact that Asian nations have their own notions about how this change trajectory should look in their societies. Their own conception of the "green" transition and sustainable development plays just as important a role as

² Communication COM/2019/640: The European Green Deal - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>

the prevailing underlying conditions and current development challenges facing the different countries of the region.³

The problem of differences in terms of vision and working methods in the relationship between the EU and states in South-East Asia, I also deepened it in other previous studies⁴, the conclusion being that although the achievements are notable, taking into account the huge geopolitical threats facing Europe and Asia (such as the Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine or US-China tensions over Taiwan), but also some global challenges (such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution), it is necessary that the leaders of EU and South-East Asian states to work together closely for maintaining peace and stability in the two regions. Regarding the particular case of the relationship between the EU and Vietnam, both parties share a common objective, in their own different ways, of strategic autonomy and have a common interest to promote a better balance in the region.

Taking into account the dynamic and positive developments of the EU-Vietnam partnership (aspects highlighted in a study that I developed together with my Vietnamese colleagues⁵), the purpose of this conference presentations is to highlight, on the one hand, the fruitful collaboration between EU and Vietnam over time, and on the other hand, is to analyse the impact of European Green Deal (EGD) on the three priority areas of the EU's bilateral cooperation with Vietnam over the period 2021-2027: Climate-responsive digital circular economy; Responsible entrepreneurship and enhanced skills for decent employment; Strengthening governance, rule of law and institutional reform.

2. The overall lines of the EU international cooperation in Vietnam

The last decades have seen a fast and strongly developing of the EU-Vietnam partnership and, as a consequence, the EU is currently one of Vietnam's largest donors of development assistance, the second largest trading partner and one of the main foreign investors in the

³ M'hamed, S. (2022). *The European Green Deal - Perspective for the EU-Asia Relationship*, Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung, Germany. Retrieved from <https://www.kas.de/en/single-title/-/content/the-european-green-deal>

⁴ Vataman, D. (2023). ASEAN-EU Partnership: Historical Development and Prospects in the Context of Indonesia's ASEAN Chairmanship in 2023. *International Journal of Humanities Education and Social Sciences*, 3(1); Vataman, D. (2023). The Establishment and Development of Diplomatic Relations and Partnership Between European Union and The Philippines. *International Journal of Humanities Education and Social Sciences*, 3(1).

⁵ Vataman, D.; Nguyen T. H.; Nguyen T.T.D. (2018). The establishment and development of diplomatic relations and partnership between European Union and Vietnam (1990-2018). *Romanian Journal of Eurasian Studies*. 14(1).

country. In turn, Vietnam is a dynamic emerging partner and wants to play an increasing role in world affairs.

The strong relationship between the two sides is also evident from the fact that no other country in South East Asia is party to as many agreements with the EU, notably the EU - Vietnam Framework Agreement on Partnership and Cooperation⁶, the EU - Vietnam Free Trade Agreement⁷, the EU - Vietnam Forest Law Enforcement⁸, the forthcoming EU - Vietnam Investment Protection Agreement (will enter into force when it is ratified by all EU Member States)⁹, Framework Participation Agreement (FPA) for the participation of Vietnam in EU crisis management operations¹⁰.

At the same time, it is important to emphasize that Vietnam, as a strategic player in the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), often supportive of enhancing the EU involvement in the region in accordance with the EU-ASEAN Strategic Partnership (2023-2027). Moreover, it should also be remembered that the EU launched the Indo-Pacific¹¹ and Global Gateway¹² Strategies in a context of accelerating geopolitical and geostrategic shifts in the region. Considering the country's regional influence, Vietnam is of particular interest, especially in light of its abstention from the UN resolution condemning the Russian invasion of Ukraine¹³.

⁶ Framework Agreement on Comprehensive Partnership and Cooperation between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, of the other part, Official Journal of the European Union L 329/3.12.2016, p. 8.

⁷ Free Trade Agreement between the European Union and the Socialist Republic of Vietnam (ST/6051/2019/INIT), Official Journal of the European Union L 186, 12.6.2020, p. 3.

⁸ Council Decision (EU) 2019/854 of 15 April 2019 on the conclusion of the Voluntary Partnership Agreement between the European Union and the Socialist Republic of Vietnam on forest law enforcement, governance and trade (ST/10861/2018/INIT), Official Journal of the European Union L 147, 5.6.2019, p. 1.

⁹ Council Decision (EU) 2019/1096 of 25 June 2019 on the signing, on behalf of the Union, of the Investment Protection Agreement between the European Union and its Member States, of the one part, and the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, of the other part (Official Journal of the European Union L 175, 28.6.2019, p. 1).

¹⁰ Agreement between the European Union and the Government of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam establishing a framework for the participation of Vietnam in European Union crisis management operations (ST/10778/2019/INIT), Official Journal of the European Union L 276, 29.10.2019, p. 3.

¹¹ Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council, *The EU strategy for cooperation in the Indo-Pacific* – JOIN (2021) 24 final, Brussels, 16.9.2021.

¹² Joint Communication to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, the Committee of the Regions and the European Investment Bank, *The Global Gateway*, JOIN (2021) 30 final.

¹³ Among the Southeast Asia's 11 countries, Brunei, Myanmar, Cambodia, Timor-Leste (East Timor), Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore and Thailand voted in favour of the resolution, with just Vietnam and Laos choosing to abstain - <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/4004933?ln=en&v=pdf>

Thus, in the light of the agreements that represent the cornerstones of the EU's relationship with Vietnam, all this within the wider framework of a strengthened EU focus on this part of the world, the 2021-2027 Multiannual Indicative Programme (MIP) for Vietnam¹⁴ will address crucial issues for the country, while promoting key areas of EU external engagement, notably green and digital transition, decent and inclusive jobs as well as good governance, the rule of law, human rights and institutional reforms. A strong EU engagement in Vietnam will allow the EU to promote sustainable and fair environmental and social norms, increase investment opportunities for EU companies, engage with non-state actors and build on the ongoing cooperation in climate action.¹⁵

Within currently context, the basis for programming is Vietnam's ten-year Social Economic Development Strategy (SEDS, 2021-2030)¹⁶ and five-year Social Economic Development Plan (SEDP, 2021-2025)¹⁷. These two together with other strategic documents, such as: the National Action Plan for the implementation of the 2030 sustainable development agenda¹⁸, the revised Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC)¹⁹, the national Green Growth Strategy (2021-2030)²⁰, the National Strategy for the Industry until 2030²¹, the programme for National Digital Transformation²².

As shown in the Multiannual Indicative Programme (MIP) for EU – Vietnam Cooperation, Vietnam's Social Economic Development Strategy (SEDS, 2021-2030) and Social Economic Development Plan

¹⁴ Commission Implementing Decision (C(2021) 8997 final) on adopting a multiannual indicative programme for Vietnam for the period 2021-2027, Brussels, 14.12.2021

¹⁵ Multiannual Indicative Programme (MIP) for EU – Vietnam Cooperation 2021-2027, p. 2.

¹⁶ Resolution of the 13th National Party Congress approving the Socio-Economic Development Strategy 2021-2030 - <https://lawnet.vn/en/vb/Resolution-2022-13th-National-Congress-7D534.html>

¹⁷ Resolution No. 16/2021/QH15 by the National Assembly approving the Socio Economic Development Plan 2021-2025 - <https://vietnam.gov.vn/socio-economic-development-plans/socio-economic-development-plan-for-2021-2025-12056314>

¹⁸ Decision 622/QĐ-TTg approving the National Action Plan for the Implementation of 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development - <https://vietnamcirculareconomy.vn/policy-library/decision-622-qd-ttg-2017>

¹⁹ https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/NDC/2022-06/Viet%20Nam_NDC_2020_Eng.pdf

²⁰ Decision No. 1658/QĐ-TTg on approving the National Strategy for Green Growth for the 2021-2030 period, with a vision toward 2050 - <https://en.baohinhphu.vn/national-green-growth-strategy-for-2021-2030-vision-towards-2050-11142515.htm>

²¹ Decision No. 2289/QĐ-TTg on adopting the National Strategy for Fourth Industrial Revolution by 2030 - <https://lawnet.vn/en/vb/Decision-No-2289-QD-TTg-2020-The-National-Strategy-for-Fourth-Industrial-Revolution-by-2030-72138.html>

²² Decision No. 749/QĐ-TTg on approving the national digital transformation program through 2025, with orientations toward 2030 - <https://english.luatvietnam.vn/decision-no-749-qd-ttg-on-approving-the-national-digital-transformation-program-until-2025-with-a-vision-184241-doc1.html>

(SEDP, 2021-2025) match EU interests and overarching priorities and are sufficiently broad in scope to cover the priority areas, as follows:

- Key elements of the European Green Deal are anchored in the Vietnam's SEDS/SEDP: the two documents encourage climate action, both climate change mitigation and adaptation, and the development of the circular economy model to increase resource efficiency. Biodiversity is mainstreamed into the chapters relating to economic growth, marine economy and natural resources. The SEDS considers water and oceans key for livelihoods, especially in the Mekong Delta, while the SEDP aims to reduce the share of untreated waste. The Government intends to tackle pollution by introducing the polluter pays principle, promptly sanctioning facilities that pollute the environment.

- Sustainable growth and development are core to the SEDS: the Government aims to create a fair, transparent and open business environment. The SEDS dedicates a chapter to education and skills, including for the pre-primary and working population in line with a life-long learning approach;

- Governance, human development: the SEDS focuses on aspects of economic and administrative governance. For example, the Government intends to continue to restructure, reform and roll out the autonomy and accountability mechanism of public service delivery units. The SEDS targets improvements of education, life expectancy and income of the population to reach a Human Development Index (HDI) above 0.7²³,

- Digital science, technology and innovation are cutting across the SEDS: the SEDS acknowledges digital as the major development trend of the era. The SEDS mentions innovation and digital transformation frequently and considers them as the breakthroughs for the period 2021-2030. Likewise, digital transition is fully endorsed making of it the highway to expected growth by 2030. There is a clear intention for independent and sustainable development, based on innovation, technology and digitalization.²⁴

3. General aspects regarding the priority areas of the EU cooperation with Vietnam over the period 2021-2027

²³ The Human Development Index (HDI) is a summary measure of average achievement in key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, being knowledgeable and having a decent standard of living. The HDI is the geometric mean of normalized indices for each of the three dimensions - <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/HDI>

²⁴ Multiannual Indicative Programme (MIP) for EU – Vietnam Cooperation 2021-2027, pp. 3-4.

EU's bilateral cooperation with Vietnam over the period 2021-2027 focuses on three priority areas, as follows: climate-responsive digital circular economy; responsible entrepreneurship and enhanced skills for decent employment; strengthening governance, rule of law and institutional reform.

As to the **climate-responsive digital circular economy**, this is the first priority area of EU action. Given the EU's frontrunner position on energy transition, it has valuable expertise for the emerging transition away from coal in Vietnam. Circular economy is a core EU strategic objective with digital technologies as a critical enabler for its upscaling, fact for which the EU has ample knowledge and experience to share and can build on its existing strong international cooperation to assist Vietnam in key policy areas of the EU's Green Deal. Taking into account that EU is recognised as a global leader on climate and environmental actions, the EU-Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA) and the Voluntary Partnership Agreement on Forest Law Enforcement Governance and Trade (VPA-FLEGT) make EU a preferred partner for Vietnam in these policy areas.

Under the second priority area of **responsible entrepreneurship and enhanced skills for decent employment**, EU interventions will achieve transformational impact through promoting a more inclusive and responsible business community and transition towards formal employment and decent work. It will be complemented by a strong push in favour of vocational training and mainstreaming of digitalisation in the workplace. These are areas where the EU and Vietnam have legally binding commitments in place (e.g. human and labour rights under the EU-Vietnam Free Trade Agreement - EVFTA) and strong ongoing engagement. This approach is expected to improve workers' skills, raise labour standards and contribute to a level playing field for European companies in Vietnam.

In the third priority area of EU action, respectively **strengthening governance, rule of law and institutional reform**, EU interventions will achieve transformational impact through supporting effective governance (including e-governance and economic governance), rule of law enforcement and institutional reform, while mainstreaming gender. Improving the quality of governance, including e-governance, is fundamental to Vietnam's prosperity and stability and requires further institutional reform. Thus, as the EU plays an important global role in

safeguarding human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, transparency, accountability, rule of law and human rights, the EU will promote these fundamental values in Vietnam.²⁵

4. The climate-responsive digital circular economy as a first priority area of action in EU-Vietnam cooperation

The European Commission adopted the new circular economy action plan (CEAP) in March 2020, as one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth. According to the CEAP, the transition to the circular economy will be systemic, deep and transformative, in the EU and beyond. It will be disruptive at times, so it has to be fair. It will require an alignment and cooperation of all stakeholders at all levels - EU, national, regional and local, and international. The EU's transition to a circular economy will reduce pressure on natural resources and will create sustainable growth and jobs. It is also a prerequisite to achieve the EU's 2050 climate neutrality target and to halt biodiversity loss.²⁶

In this context, the EU is committed to supporting Vietnam's journey towards sustainable and inclusive development, aligning its efforts with the 2021-2030 Vietnam Socio-Economic Development Strategy (SEDS), the Vietnam Green Growth Strategy, and the EU's Global Gateway and Indo-Pacific Strategies.

The EU's engagement is rooted in the Multiannual Indicative Programme (MIP) for EU – Vietnam Cooperation 2021-2027 which sets out three priority areas described above, the first of these being **climate-responsive digital circular economy**. Under this priority area, EU interventions will achieve transformational impact through climate resilience building, low-carbon transition in key economic sectors, environmental protection and a more sustainable and digital management of resource flows.

Regarding EU action in on **climate resilience**, the activities include support for communities in the most climate vulnerable urban and rural areas to adapt to climate variability and the unavoidable local impacts of climate change, which are emerging drivers of migration. The focus will be on infrastructure, livelihoods, awareness raising and change management towards more sustainable and digital practices.

²⁵ Ibid, pp. 5, 12 and 15.

²⁶ A new Circular Economy Action Plan: For a cleaner and more competitive Europe (COM/2020/98 final)
- <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>

The possible application of digital technologies to the agriculture sector may contribute to a greener growth and a reduced environmental impact²⁷. Where possible, nature-based solutions will be preferred. The main focus is on *Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 13: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*, one of the 17 SDGs enshrined by the *2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development* launched by a UN Summit in New York on 25-27 September 2015²⁸.

As power demand grows, Vietnam needs to boost energy efficiency and tap into various energy sources, including coal, natural gas, wind, solar and hydropower, to ensure sustainable, reliable and affordable power supply. Keen to promote a **low-carbon development** pathway that decouples economic growth from energy consumption, delivers on Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC)²⁹ targets and reduces dependency on fossil fuels, the EU will continue its support to the Vietnam Government programme on energy efficiency, coal phase out, the energy-digital nexus and the enabling environment for private sector investments in energy efficiency and renewable energy. Transition from coal to gas (particularly Liquefied Natural Gas) and supply side management could reduce greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) in the energy sector in an intermediary phase but a direct transition to renewable energy will be encouraged. Industry will continue to be a key player to reduce energy intensity. The EU will also explore opportunities to support the development of smart grids as enabler of the energy transition in Vietnam, and the roll out of green, smart and affordable mobility. Thus, an important element in EU action is reaching the target set in *Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7: Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy*. As shown in MIP 2021-2027, local authorities, non-state actors and even citizens of all ages are key drivers of an energy transition. It is important to ensure that this transition is just (e.g. risk of electricity price increase in power mix scenarios with high variable renewable energy penetration). Mainstreaming women participation in the energy

²⁷ Currently Vietnam's agriculture is facing unprecedented challenges due to erratic rainfall, rising temperatures, and extreme weather events. These pressures threaten the entire food chain, as climate change substantially disrupts the traditional weather-based agriculture practices.

²⁸ Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development - <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/>

²⁹ Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) is a climate action plan to cut emissions and adapt to climate impacts. Each Party to the Paris Agreement is required to establish an NDC and update it every five years - <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/all-about-ndcs>

transition at all levels (decision-making, education, private sector, utilities) shall be given priority.⁵⁰

As regards to the field of **environmental protection**, the EU action can support the strengthening of environmental regulation – including enforcement – and management capacity, coupled with a good mix of environmental policy instruments. Cooperation on specific issues such as deforestation should be pursued, including through the continuation of the Voluntary Partnership Agreement on Forest Law Enforcement Governance and Trade (VPA-FLEGT) as well as through the development and establishment of a forest partnership. It is key to leverage further action through a win-win approach to halt deforestation and forest degradation through sustainable forest management, promote sustainable agricultural and forest value chains, foster good forest governance and enhance forest-based economic, social and environmental benefits, including by improving the livelihoods of forest-dependent people (in line with the EU Communication on protecting and restoring the world's forests, the upcoming EU legislation on deforestation-free supply chains, the Convention on Biodiversity, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the Paris Agreement adopted under the UNFCCC, CITES, the Global Forests Goals of the UN Strategic Plan for Forests 2030, and other international forest related instruments, processes, commitments and goals)⁵¹

Related to the climate-responsive digital circular economy as a first priority area of action in EU-Vietnam cooperation a number of three specific objectives were set, together with the expected results for each of them:

1. Strengthened resilience to climate related hazards and natural disasters: Vietnam's overall resilience to more frequent climate related hazards and natural disasters, mainly due to the unavoidable impact of climate change, will be strengthened through more climate resilient local communities and livelihoods in line with *Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 13: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts*. The results expected for this objective: more climate change resilient local communities and their livelihoods.

2. Greener, smart, and more efficient energy consumption and production: Vietnam's energy production and consumption is greener,

⁵⁰ Multiannual Indicative Programme (MIP) for EU – Vietnam Cooperation 2021-2027, p. 9.

⁵¹ *Ibid.*, pp. 9-10.

smarter and more efficient through increased renewable energy and enhanced energy efficiency in line with *Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7: Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy*. Therefore, continued EU support to the Government programme on energy efficiency and the enabling environment for private sector investments in energy efficiency together with digitalisation and supply/demand side management is expected to significantly enhance energy efficiency. Another expected outcome for this specific objective relates to share of renewable energy in the power generation mix is increased. On this line, continued EU support to the Vietnam Government strategy on the promotion of renewable energy together with support for coal phase out and development of smart grids is expected to result in an increased share of renewables in the power mix. This will in turn facilitate the electrification of transport and the roll out of green, smart and affordable mobility.

3. *Conserved natural resources*: Sustainable and deforestation free supply chains are promoted and overall consumption and production practices are more sustainable, through strengthened forest and protected area management. Regarding this specific objective is expected as a result that forest and protected area management is strengthened and sustainable and deforestation free supply chains are promoted. It is also considered that EU funding for Sustainable Consumption and Production (known as SCP) actions combined with awareness raising campaigns is expected to improve the overall environmental performance of products throughout their life cycle, stimulate demand for better products and production technologies and help consumers make informed choices.³²

5. Conclusions

As the Executive Vice-President and Commissioner for Trade Valdis Dombrovskis pointed out at the Green Economy Forum 2023, event themed "Empowering Vietnam's Sustainable Landscape: European-Vietnamese Collaboration Fuels Green Initiatives", Vietnam is not only an important partner for the EU in the Indo-Pacific region, but above all, Vietnam is a "very ambitious partner who has set big goals – internationally and domestically"³³.

³² Ibid, pp. 10-11.

³³ Speech by Executive Vice-President Dombrovskis at the Green Economy Forum - https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/speech_23_5501

Thus, in the context of the most important commitment of the European Green Deal, respectively the EU's unwavering determination to be climate-neutral by 2050 – an economy with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions, Vietnam, too, has declared its ambition to become net zero by that year. So, it can be said that both the EU and Vietnam share a common objective and in the framework of their unwavering dedication to sustainable economic growth, the partnership between the EU and Vietnam stands as a noteworthy example and model.

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